

Effects Of Trunk Exercises On Balance Among Children With Cerebral Palsy

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 10, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: December 11, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Determine, Children, The Research, The Study Design</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7424593</p>	<p><i>The objective of the study is to determine the effects of trunk exercises on balance among children with cerebral palsy.</i></p> <p><i>The study design is a Quasi-experimental study. The research is conducted in Al-Farabi center, Islamabad. Study duration is 6 months and the sample size is 30 patients; while the sampling technique is non-probability convenience sampling technique. Sample selection is according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The data is collected in three phases that is at baseline, after 4 weeks and after 8 weeks' treatment. The data is collected through general demographic questionnaire, & Pediatric Berg Balance Scale. The data is analysed using SPSS version 21. Categorical variables are presented as frequency and percentages while continuous variables are presented as Mean±SD. Repeated Measure ANOVA is measured for within the group analysis.</i></p> <p><i>Category wise result of Pediatric Balance Scale shows out of N=30, n=2 (6.7%) are lying in the medium fall risk category & high fall risk n=28 (93.3 %) at baseline. After 4th week of treatment n=30 (100%) are lying in the medium fall risk category and n=16 (53.3%) in low risk fall while after 8th week of treatment n=14(46.7%) in medium fall risk category. Within the group analysis shows significant improvement in overall total score of Pediatric Berg Balance Scale between baseline & after 4th week treatment, 4th week & 8th week treatment and baseline & 8th week treatment.</i></p> <p><i>Within the group analysis shows significant improvement in overall total score Pediatric Berg Balance Scale between baseline & after 4th week treatment, 4th week & 8th week treatment and baseline & 8th week treatment</i></p>

Introduction

Cerebral Palsy (CP) is described as a permanent but non progressive impairment of the immature brain that is affected in the prenatal, perinatal or postnatal period [1]. Spastic type of CP is the most prevalent variant (up to 70%), which is characterized with muscle tone increase. Contractures and deformities which are proportionally consisted with the type and severity of CP can lead to postural disorders. Abnormal motor patterns, immature trunk control, abnormal tone and disorder of postural control are affecting children's physical development negatively [2].

Most researches for postural control in CP are studying the changes of gravity responses of lower extremity balance perturbation, standing position and then starting to walk or they are about trunk control primary for sitting. These researches show that for children with CP, independent sitting balance and trunk control are important for walking [3]. Similarly, head control is important for postural control and balance ability [4]. In normal developmental processes, as the development of the vertebral extensor progresses from the head to feet, the erector muscle of the upper thorax begins to become stronger and has the ability to regulate antigravity [5]. Several studies have addressed improving balance ability among children with cerebral palsy. Choi et al. reports that trunk muscle strengthening exercises positively affects the upper limb functions and balance ability among children with cerebral palsy [6]. Similarly, McBurney et al. reports that when lower limb muscle strengthening exercises are applied to 11 spastic paraplegic children with cerebral palsy, lower limb muscle strength, flexibility, postures, and gait ability are improved; this study's findings also emphasized the importance of strengthening exercises for improving trunk stability [7]. Therefore, many researchers have suggested that balance perturbation intervention should be a crucial component of any regular rehabilitation program for these children. It is able to modify postural balance control and establish correct posture in the line of gravity [8].

Two types of balance training have been studied in children with CP. One type is based on using a moving platform for repetitive stance perturbation to improve their stability recovery after an external perturbation [9]. The second type of balance training aims to improve the patients' awareness about their

postural sway by using visual feedback during unperturbed stance [10]. Concomitantly, there are a number of tests for measuring balance performance and detecting posture deficits. The most commonly effective methods used in balance analysis laboratories is the use of a balance platform [11]

Materials & Methods

The study design is Quasi-experimental study. The research is conducted in Al-Farabi center, Islamabad. Study duration is 6 months after the ethical permission by the head of the organization. The sample size is 30 patients [130]. Non-probability convenience sampling technique is used. Following exercise protocol is followed; Hot packs have been applied for 10 minutes at upper & lower limb before the treatment session. Total Duration of the treatment is 38-40 minutes.

EXERCISES	Frequency	Duration	Set
crook lying position pelvic bridging	6 times	10 sec/ frequency	3
unilateral bridging,	6 times	10 sec/ frequency	3
upper trunk rotation	6 times	10 sec/ frequency	3
bringing clasp hand on either side	6 times	10 sec/ frequency	3
Flexion of upper trunk	6 times	10 sec/ frequency	3
in stool sitting flexion extension of lower trunk,	6 times	10 sec/ frequency	3
rotation of upper and lower trunk	6 times	10 sec/ frequency	3
in kneeling and half kneeling trunk rotation	6 times	10 sec/ frequency	3
forward and lateral reach	6 times	10 sec/ frequency	3

The sample is selected according to the Inclusion criteria & exclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria is Cerebral palsy child having age limit 6-14 with Gross motor function of grade I and II according to Gross Motor Function Classification System [28]. Degree of spasticity is between grade 1 and 2 according to Modified Ashworth Scale [29]. While the Exclusion criteria is as follow; 1) If patient underwent any surgical procedure i.e., lengthening or scoliosis surgery. 2) If patient had dorsal rhizotomy. 3) Patients experienced botulinum toxin injection to lower extremity. 4) Secondary orthopedic complication due to neurodegenerative disease. 5) Children with visual, auditory and vestibular perceptual deficit.

The data is collected in three phases i.e at baseline, after 4 weeks and after 8 weeks' treatment. Data is collected through the General demographic questionnaire at baseline & Pediatric Berg Balance Scale at baseline, after 6 weeks & after 12 weeks' treatment. The data is analysed using SPSS version 21. Categorical variables are presented as frequency and percentages while continuous variables are presented as Mean \pm SD. Repeated Measure ANOVA is measured for within the group analysis.

RESULT

The Mean \pm SD age is 10.60 \pm 2.62 years. Within the group analysis shows significant improvement in overall total score of Pediatric Berg Balance Scale between baseline & after 4th week treatment, 4th week & 8th week treatment and baseline & 8th week treatment.

The details of demographic data & Pediatric berg balance scale are shown below;

Table1: Demographic data of Various Variables

Variables		Frequency/Mean	Percent/SD
Gender	Male	18	60.0
	Female	12	40.0
Gross Motor Function Classification Scale	level1	7	23.3
	level2	23	76.7
Modified Asworth Scale	grade1	10	33.3
	grade2	20	66.7
Height (ft.inch)		3.55	.798

Age(years)	10.60	2.62
Weight(kg)	27.367	8.23
Birth weight(pounds)	4.34	.48
Gestational Age(week)	38.63	.96

Table 2: Category wise results of Pediatric Balance Scale

		Frequency	Percent
Baseline	medium fall risk	2	6.7
	high risk fall	28	93.3
After 4th week treatment	medium fall risk	30	100
	high risk fall	0	0
After 8th week treatment	low risk fall	16	53.3
	medium fall risk	14	46.7
	high risk fall	0	0

Table 3: Mean, SD and p-value of Total Score of Pediatric Balance Scale

TotalScore	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Baseline	12.47	5.37	0.00a
after Week4 treatment	26.50	4.19	0.00b
after Week8 treatment	40.50	4.13	0.00c

a = Baseline vs Week 4

b = Week 4 vs Week 8

c = Week 8 vs Baseline

DISCUSSION

Factors that cause or influence the “gait outcomes” maybe called determinants and the quality of trunk control maybe taken as one such determinant. The measurement of the outcomes and their determinants is said to be essential for informing decisions about treatment and targeting of CP patients. In this regard ‘Sitting’ and ‘Gait’ with ‘sitting’ as classical assessment for balance a quantitative measure are considered to be among the current methods for assessing stability in disease conditions of CP (12).

Quite large number of Trunk control studies has been carried out with CP patients using varied experimental tools on the lower limb and extremities (13, 14). Keeping in view the outcomes of the so far studies, it seems important to address the factor of impairment which was observed in gait control experiments and to establish relationship between the trunk control activity(ies) (15, 16).

This Quasi experimental study has therefore been undertaken with the CP patients of the average age at the Al-Farabi Center, Islamabad for the duration of six months where non-probability convenience sampling technique was followed. The exercise protocol comprised of 9-positions. Total Duration of the treatment was 38-40 minutes for every set of 3-applications and with a duration of 10sec/frequency (6-times for each set).

The study pattern for Pediatric Berg Balance Scale (PBBS) with 14 items scale and a maximum 54 score has been followed for each item. Multiple trials are conducted. The child performance score is based upon the lowest criteria, which describes the child’s best performance. If on the first trial a child receives the maximal score of 4, additional trials need not to be administered. [17].

Pediatric Berg Balance Scale (Appendix 4) is collected at baseline, after 6 weeks and after 12 weeks’ treatment. The data is analyzed using SPSS version 21. Categorical variables are presented as frequency and percentages while continuous variables are presented as Mean±SD. Repeated Measure ANOVA is measured for within the group analysis.

According to the category-wise result, Out of N=30, n=2 (6.7%) are lying in the medium fall risk category & high risk fall n=28 (93.3 %) at baseline. After 4th week of treatment n=30 (100%) are lying in the medium fall risk category and n=16 (53.3%) in low risk fall, n=14(46.7%) in medium fall risk category after 8th week of treatment. (Table 4). In most of the cases best of 3-trials have been recorded for each of the 14-tasks, score of 0-4 data assessment using SPSS and differences are noted in seconds.

Significant Difference are found between the total score of Pediatric Balance Scale Baseline & after 4th week of treatment, after 4th week of treatment & after 8th week of treatment and between Baseline & after 8th week of treatment. (Table 5). Franjoine 2021 have carried out an Examination of the effects of age, sex, and motor ability level on balance capabilities in children with cerebral palsy GMFCS levels I, II, III and typical development using the Pediatric Balance Scale, they administered PBS to 477 children 24 through 59 months: 258 with typical development (TD) and 219 with CP GMFCS levels I, II and III. [17]

Children's performance on individual items is analyzed by age, sex and motor ability level. They carry out 3-way ANOVA where PBS scores are significantly affected by age ($F_4, 437=26.95, p<0.0001, \eta^2p=0.198$), motor ability level ($F_3, 437=482.15, p<0.0001, \eta^2p=0.768$) and sex ($F_1, 437=4.64, p<0.03, \eta^2p=0.01$) with significant interaction between motor ability level and age ($F_{12,437}=5.25, p<0.001, \eta^2p=0.126$). Under the overall assessment Children with TD outperformed children with CP GMFCS level I 36-59 months and children with CP GMFCS levels II and III 24-59 months.

Expected performance values for children with TD and children with CP, ages 24-59 months, at GMFCS levels I, II and III. Sharma, P. and Thapar, S. (2018) are also significantly improved. Valid and reliable functional balance measures are therefore of critical importance if the pediatric physical therapist is to justify that intervention is warranted and demonstrated that improve balance function has occurred as a result of intervention.[18]

Sibley, K.M. et al. (2011) Pediatric physical therapists have examined balance through the observation of the underlying elements of the balance response, timed measures of static postures, and standardized developmental measures of gross motor function.[19]

The ability to describe the extent to which a child demonstrates righting reactions protective responses and equilibrium reactions in response to a therapist generated perturbation formed the foundation of the "classic" balance assessment. The Pediatric Balance Scale (PBS), a modification of Berg's Balance Scale, is developed as a balance measure for school-age children with mild to moderate motor impairments.

The clinician may predict the ability of the child to safely and independently function in a variety of environments (i.e. home, school, and community). However El-Shamy & Ebd El Kafy studied on the evaluation of the effects of balance training on postural control and fall risk in children with diplegic cerebral palsy. With thirty spastic diplegic cerebral palsied children (10–12 years) are randomly assigned into two equal-sized groups: control and study groups. Participants in both groups have received a traditional physical therapy exercise program. The study group additionally receive balance training on the Biodex balance system. [20]

As a result of the study it is revealed that Children in both groups show significant improvements in the mean values of all measured variables post-treatment ($p<0.05$). The results also show significantly better improvement in the measured parameters for the study group, as compared to the control group ($p<0.05$). It is revealed that Balance training is a useful tool that can be used in improving postural balance control in children with diplegic cerebral palsy (with Biodex balance System as well.

Like the above mentioned study, the results of this study also show that Balance control is important in the competence in the performance of most functional skills as well the Balance training in children with cerebral palsy can improve performance in postural control. Ragab et al. (2021) has also worked upon the Effectiveness of a Multi-Modal Exercise Program Incorporating Plyometric and Balance Training in Children with Hemiplegic Cerebral Palsy using a Three-Armed Randomized Clinical Trial. [21]

Results reveal that the Incorporation of plyometric and balance exercises in a multimodal rehabilitation program could be an important consideration for enhancing and boosting postural stability in children with Cerebral Palsy.

CONCLUSION

Within the group analysis show significant improvement in overall total score of Pediatric Berg Balance Scale between baseline & after 4th week treatment, 4th week & 8th week treatment and baseline & 8th week treatment.

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